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Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Parasites in Chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*); Case Study Somali Poultry Farm in Mogadishu, Somalia.

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Abstract

*The objective of this study to known the common gastrointestinal parasites in a chicken case study of Somali poultry farm, Mogadishu Somalia. To get this objective researcher demonstrated the experimental laboratory of fecal examination. **Methods:** The target population was 45 chickens in the Somali Poultry farm in Mogadishu as a case study. The researcher was selected 40 chickens as the sample size to collect their drops. Sampling technique was selected non-probability sampling, and purposive sampling techniques. The data were collected from the study area, and entered the SPSS statistical computer software (SPSS version 16) and significance P value was used.*

***Results:** The prevalence of positive chickens after investigation was 31 (77.5%) and negative chickens was 9 (22.5%) (Table 03). In found the prevalence of various different parasites was observed in positive chickens and some had mixed infections. The parasites that were observed consisted of six parasites (**Nematoda** - *Ascaris gallus*, **Protozoa**-*Coccidia* (*Eimeria spp.*), **Cestoda** – *Tapeworm* (*Raillietina spp.*), **Protozoa** - *Gairdia spp.* **Nematoda**-*Heterogali aksia*, and **Nematoda** - *capillaria spp*). The highest percentage of parasites in chickens was coccidian (*Eimeria spp.*) 19 (47.5%), the second highest prevalence rate was nematoda *Ascaris gallus spp* and *Cestoda* or *Tapeworm* (*Raillietina spp*) which have 13(32.5%), the third highest prevalence rate was **Protozoa** - *Gairdia spp*; which has 11(27.5%), fourth prevalence parasite which was seen in chickens. **Nematoda** - *Heterogali aksia*, which has 3 (7.5%); and the last parasite prevalence in some chickens was **Nematoda** - *capillaria spp*, 1 (2.5%), with all having a significant P value of ($P = 0.000$). So finally, this study determined the common parasitic infections that dominant in the Somali poultry farm in Daynile, Mogadishu Somalia. **Recommendation:** To carry out seasonal or monthly based campaigns that massively deworming chicken to carriers and prevalent cases. Must use specifically anti-nematoda, anti-cestoda, and antiprotozoal drugs that can effectively eliminate parasitic infections.*

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, chicken, gastrointestinal parasites, Somalia

1.0.Introduction

In Somalia, Gastrointestinal Parasites are endemic, causing economic losses: particularly in local growing birds in all areas. In the recent year's parasitic disease of chicken was the most important cause of mortalities and morbidity. The most common parasite was Coccidiosis, which has been reported as one of the major disease problems of chicken production in spite of advances made in prevention and control through chemotherapy. [12]. So this study investigated the prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites on chicken case study Somali Poultry Farm in Mogadishu.

The objective of this study to know the common gastrointestinal parasites in a chicken case study of Somali poultry farm: Mogadishu Somalia. To get this objective researcher demonstrated the experimental laboratory of fecal examination. This study is important to discover the existing parasites of chickens in Somali poultry farms.

Poultry products throughout the world are one of the most important protein sources for humans, but in Somalia: recent days learned the use of poultry as food some place but the other Somali Agro-pastoralists used local chicken in home yards. As FAO mentioned that the prevalence of most parasitic diseases in poultry seems to have been reduced significantly in commercial indoor poultry production systems due to improved housing, hygiene, and management. However, parasitic diseases continue to be of great importance in deep-litter and free-range commercial systems. [1]

The aim of this study was to increase our knowledge of the prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chicken flocks in a case study of only one farm (Somali poultry farm), at district Daynile, Mogadishu Somalia.

The findings of this study serve as guidance for the poultry owner farmers, local authorities, community animal health workers, Veterinary NGO's and the international community operating the capital Mogadishu, so as to address some common gastrointestinal parasites of chicken, can have useful to the whole health of the community. The findings of this study will provide research based on up-to-date information for future researchers.

2.0.Literature review

Debbou-Iouknane, N., et al. (2018) found that after Necropsy and parasitological examinations were carried out using standard methods. Of the samples examined, 93 out of the 147 litter samples and 78 out of the 109 intestinal content samples were infected with *Eimeria* oocysts. [2]

K.L. Adang et al. (2014) in Gombe State, Nigeria found that the helminths identified from chickens comprised of *Railleitina tetragona* 52 (34.7%), *R. cesticillus* 32 (21.3%), *R. echinobothrida* 38 (25.3%), *R. magninumida* 5 (3.3%), *Amoebotaenia cuneata* 6 (4.0%), *Hymenolepis carioca* 18 (12.0%), and *Ascaridia galli* 16 (10.7%) [8].

Razmi, G. R., & Kalideri, G. A. (2000), Also they got after Eighty-four chicken farms were randomly selected from each farm, five birds per 10 000 were sampled (as was litter). Serial scraping of the intestinal lining was done in chicks at 3rd and >6th weeks of age. so the farm-level prevalence of subclinical coccidiosis was 38%. [3]

Bachaya, H. A. et al. (2012). They studied the predominance and detection of different eimeria species causing coccidiosis in layer chickens of the district Muzaffar garh in Pakistan. They found that four different species of *Eimeria* i.e. *E. maxima*, (30.20%), *E. tenella*, (39.93%), *E. mitis*, (19.13%), and *E. necatrix* (10.74 %) were isolated from 298/500 (59.60%) infected gut samples. [4]

Adhikari, A. et al. (2008) Found that the Monthwise highest prevalence rate (50%) was observed in March and the lowest (10%) in the months of April and September. Seasonwise prevalence showed the highest prevalence rate (33%) in the summer and spring, and the lowest (14%) in autumn. The agewise prevalence was the highest (48%) in the 31-45 days age group and the least (6%) in 0-15 days age group of layers. [5]

In Jatau I. D, et al. (2012), in Nigeria, they studied the prevalence of *Coccidia* infection in Zaria, Nigeria. All seven *Eimeria* species of chickens were identified with overall prevalences: *E. maxima* (58.6%), *E. acervulina* (47.1%), *E. mitis* (30.0%), *E. brunetti* (28.6%), *E. tenella* (22.9%), and *E. praecox* (8.6%). Mixed *Eimeria* species infections were common among the sampled chickens, with an overall prevalence of 61.4%. [6]

Kaboudi K. et al. (2016) they study the prevalence of coccidiosis: the overall rate of coccidiosis was 31.8%: *E. tenella* (61.5%), *E. maxima* (12%), and *E. acervulina* (1.5%). Mixed *Eimeria*

species infection was observed, with an overall prevalence of 26.5%. There was a statistically significant difference among infection rates, age groups, season, diarrhea, and type of chicken. [7]

3.0. Material and methods

3.1. Study area: Somali poultry farm is located in Daynile district, Mogadishu Somalia. It has different floor houses and the total number of chickens was near 12,000 (estimation), the time we visited was 3 days (12, 13, and 14 May 2019).

3.2 Research Design

This study followed explanatory research and a survey laboratory stool examination. It is quantitative in nature. The research was started on 12 May, 2019. The data were collected on four (4) days 12-15 May, 2018. September 2019 ended the integration of data.

3.3 Area of Study

The study was conducted in Mogadishu, the capital city of Somalia, particularly Daynile district, a case study in Somali poultry farm. Daynile is one of the districts located southeast of the Mogadishu Benadir region, but research collected samples to Somali poultry farm located in the village Ciise Cabdi near ex Radio Horn Africa.

3.4. Sample size

The target population was 45 chickens in the Somali Poultry farm in Mogadishu as a case of study. Forty five chickens were selected forty chickens as the sample size to collect their drops. As a result, the sample size was calculated as this formula used Slovene's formula, which is $n = N / (1 + (N * e^2))$, where n the sample size, N the population size, and e the margin of error of 5%. Sampling technique was selected for nonprobability sampling and purposive sampling techniques.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data were collected through laboratory diagnosis using a compound microscope. The researcher used direct and flotation methods to detect the morphology of eggs, oocytes, and cysts of parasites in chickens. Then, the parasites were identified microscopically as defined by Cheng (1973), and Soulsby (1982). The data were collected from the study area, and entered the SPSS statistical computer software (SPSS version 16) and significance P value was used.

4.0 Result

The researcher got a common prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chickens after examination of fecal samples from Somali poultry farm in Daynile district of Benadir regions Somalia. The prevalence of positive chickens after investigation was 31 (77.5%) and negative chickens was 9 (22.5%) (Table 03). In found the prevalence of various different parasites was observed in positive chickens and some had mixed infections.

Table 01: **Parasite presence of chicken**

Parasite presence of chicken				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Positive	31	77.5	77.5
	Negative	9	22.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	

Source: Primary data

The prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chicken was practically examined for chicken drops of chicken irrespective of the sex of chickens, but the researcher focused on the presence of parasites in the drops. The parasites that were observed consisted of six parasites (**Nematoda - *Ascaris gallus***, **Protozoa-Coccidia ((*Eimeria spp.*)**, **Cestoda – Tapeworm (*Raillietina spp.*)**, **Protozoa - *Gairdia spp.***, **Nematoda - *Heterogali aksia***, and **Nematoda - *capillaria spp.***). The highest percentage of parasites in chickens was coccidian (***Eimeria spp.***: 19 (47.5%), the second highest prevalence rate was nematoda *Ascaris gallus* spp and Cestoda or Tapeworm (*Raillietina spp.*). which had 13(32.5%), and the third highest prevalence rate was **Protozoa - *Gairdia spp.***: which has 11(27.5%), fourth prevalence parasite which was seen in chickens **Nematoda-*Heterogali aksia***, which has 3 (7.5%), and the last parasite prevalence in some chickens was **Nematoda - *capillaria spp.*** 1 (2.5%), with all having a significant P value of (P = 0.000).

Table 02: Prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chickens

Prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chickens			
	N	N of P +ve	Percentage
Nematoda - Ascaris gallus	40	13	32.5%
Nematoda - Heterogali aksia	40	3	7.5%
Nematoda - Capillaria spp	40	1	2.5%
Cestoda or Tapeworm (Raillietina spp)	40	13	32.5%
Protozoa - Gairdia spp	40	11	27.5%
Protozoa – Coccidia spp	40	19	47.5%
	240	60	25%

Source: Primary data

This Table 03 shows the significance P value of all data in SPSS with a one-sample test. After that researcher had used test value 3, the result had P value or Significance (2-tailed) = 0.000, which means the test is significant because the researcher used the rule below: If $P > 0.05$ The test is not significant (the sample is not significantly different from $\mu = 3$). Finally, the analysis of the of sample test showed that the dominant answer to that question is significant no difference at all.

Table 03: Significance P-values.

One-Sample Test						
	Test Value = 3					
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
					Lower	Upper
Ascaris Gallus	-17.667	39	.000	-1.325	-1.48	-1.17

Heterogali aksia	-25.488	39	.000	-1.075	-1.16	-.99
Capillaria spp	-41.000	39	.000	-1.025	-1.08	-.97
Raillietina spp	-17.667	39	.000	-1.325	-1.48	-1.17
Gairdia spp	-17.832	39	.000	-1.275	-1.42	-1.13
Coccidias	-18.446	39	.000	-1.475	-1.64	-1.31

Source: Primary data

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, we examined 40 fecal samples of chickens collected from one poultry farm known as Somali poultry farm and revealing the overall prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in chickens in the investigated farm was 77.5% that means 31 samples were positive, and 9 samples were negative for gastrointestinal parasites. Some were mixed parasitic infections 20 samples out of 31 positive samples were mixed.

Protozoan parasites such as coccidian (*Eimeria spp.*) were the most highest percentage of parasites in chickens, which was 19 (47.5%), as Debbou-Iouknane N. et al. (2018), found 93 out of the 147 chicken drop samples and 78 out of the 109 intestinal content samples were infected with *Eimeria* oocysts [2][3][4][7]. Therefore with coccidian can occur in subclinical stages or asymptomatic stages and in clinical form, when the parasites are subclinical you can be detected the fecal examination.

The Nematoda *Ascaris gallus* spp and Cestoda or Tapeworm (*Raillietina spp.*) were the second highest prevalence rates that observed in chicken drops with 13(32.5%), and Nematoda *Ascaris gallus* was most the prevalent in chickens that had direct contact with the drops of other chickens. The **Protozoa** - *Gairdia spp* was the third highest prevalence rates, which has 11(27.5%), and **Nematoda** - *Heterogali aksia*, were the fourth most prevalent parasite: which was seen in chickens that had 3 (7.5%): The last parasite prevalence in some chickens was **Nematoda** - *capillaria spp.* 1 (2.5%). Murthy, G. S. S., et al. (2014) studied gastrointestinal parasites of poultry and found that the prevalence of *Capillaria sp.* and *Eimeria sp.* in poultry was 7.0 and 6.0 %, respectively. [11]. Finally: this study determined the common parasitic infections that dominant in the Somali poultry farm in Daynile, Mogadishu Somalia.

Any researchers willing to undertake further studies in this area are advised to make survey local chicken breeds in all districts for their parasites in Mogadishu Somalia. Also they can search for the external parasite of chickens in Somalia.

6.0. Recommendation

The Researcher recommends making continuous monitoring and treatment of farm chickens to get effective production with less time and is also recommended to check the direct of chickens to the birds near it; that the possible ways in which parasites can transmit between them. To give the chicken with safe and adequate nutrition to get more immunity will reduce the prevalence of parasites to chickens, and to give training to farm workers how to clean the chicken house and environment.

To carry out seasonal or monthly based campaigns that massively de-worming chicken to carriers and prevalent cases. Must use specifically anti-nematoda, anti-cestoda, and antiprotozoal drugs that can effectively eliminate parasitic infections.

7.0. Acknowledgements

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